

Large Language Model for Qualitative Research - Systematic Mapping Study

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Systematic mapping with the objective of identifying studies that use LLMs for qualitative analysis.

Planning

To find studies that used LLMs for qualitative analysis, including processes such as training, data analyzed, and LLM-based tools.

To investigate the state of the art regarding the relationship between LLMs and qualitative analysis.

Research Questions

1. What is the context in which LLMs have been applied to support qualitative analysis?
2. Which LLM model and configuration were used, and what data sources were utilized?
3. How was the LLM used to conduct qualitative analysis, and which techniques or methodologies were applied?
4. How was the effectiveness of the LLM evaluated, and what were the main results?
5. What limitations and future research directions were reported?

Keywords and Synonyms

Keyword	Synonyms
LLM	LLMs, Large Language Model, Large Language Models, Massive Language Model
Open Coding	
Qualitative Analysis	Grounded Theory, Qualitative Research
Survey	

Search String

("LLM" OR "LLMs" OR "Large Language Model" OR "Large Language Models") AND ("Qualitative Analysis" OR "Qualitative Research" OR "Grounded Theory")

Sources

- ACM Digital Library (<http://portal.acm.org>)

- Arxiv (<https://arxiv.org>)
- IEEE Digital Library (<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>)
- ISI Web of Science (<http://www.isiknowledge.com>)
- SBC (<https://sol.sbc.org.br/busca/>)
- Scopus (<http://www.scopus.com>)

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Discusses the use of LLM in the open coding phase
- Discusses the use of LLM for qualitative analysis

Exclusion Criteria:

- Not published in journals or scientific conference proceedings
- Does not discuss the use of LLM in the open coding phase
- Does not discuss the use of LLM for qualitative analysis
- Not written in Portuguese or English
- Duplicate publication
- No full access to the text

Data Extraction Form

- Publication
- Source
- Is the primary focus of the study to analyze the use of LLMs to support qualitative data analysis?
- What was the context of the qualitative analysis?
- What was the main objective of the study in applying LLM to qualitative analysis?
- Which LLM model was used?
- Was the model fine-tuned or adapted for the study?
- What data sources were analyzed?
- How was the qualitative analysis process conducted using the LLM?
- Were specific techniques/methodologies employed to support the analysis?
- What techniques were used or evaluated?
- Was any established qualitative analysis framework used?
- Does the paper detail the prompt engineering process?
- What metrics or criteria were used to evaluate the effectiveness of the LLM in qualitative analysis?
- Did the study compare the LLM-based analysis with traditional qualitative analysis methods?
- If the answer to question 12 is yes, was the LLM better, worse, or equivalent to traditional methods?
- Were specific limitations identified in using LLMs for qualitative analysis?

- Are there any recommendations or suggestions from the authors for the use or future development of LLMs in qualitative analyses?

Conducting

Digital Libraries Search Strings

ACM Digital Library:

APPLICATION DATE: 10/05/2024

STUDIES RETURNED: 20

[[Abstract: "llm"] OR [Abstract: "llms"] OR [Abstract: "large language model"] OR [Abstract: "large language models"]] AND [[Abstract: "qualitative analysis"] OR [Abstract: "qualitative research"] OR [Abstract: "grounded theory"]]

Arxiv:

APPLICATION DATE: 11/14/2024

Included studies: 1

https://arxiv.org/search/?query=LLM+AND+%22qualitative+research%22&searchtype=title&abstracts=show&order=-announced_date_first&size=50

APPLICATION DATE: 28/01/2025

Manual Included studies: 1

IEEE Digital Library:

APPLICATION DATE: 10/03/2024

STUDIES RETURNED: 30

("All Metadata":"LLM" OR "All Metadata":"LLMs" OR "All Metadata":"Large Language Model" OR "All Metadata":"Large Language Models") AND ("All Metadata":"Qualitative Analysis" OR "All Metadata":"Qualitative Research" OR "All Metadata":"Grounded Theory")

ISI Web of Science:

APPLICATION DATE: 10/05/2024

STUDIES RETURNED: 78

TS=(("LLM" OR "LLMs" OR "Large Language Model" OR "Large Language Models") AND (

"Qualitative Analysis" OR "Qualitative Research" OR "Grounded Theory"))

Copy query link:

<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/summary/2cd56911-7a59-4ed9-92f8-ddd4aff823c5-010e58f219/relevance/1>

Topic (TS) = Searches title, abstract, keyword plus, and author keywords.

SBC:

APPLICATION DATE: 10/18/2024

STUDIES RETURNED: 32

TITLE&ABS ("LLM" OR "LLMs" OR "Large Language Model" OR "Large Language Models")

Scopus:

APPLICATION DATE: 10/03/2024

STUDIES RETURNED: 193

TITLE-ABS-KEY(("LLM" OR "LLMs" OR "Large Language Model" OR "Large Language Models") AND ("Qualitative Analysis" OR "Qualitative Research" OR "Grounded Theory"))

Imported Studies

- **ACM Digital Library:** 20
- **Arxiv:** 2
- **IEEE Digital Library:** 30
- **ISI Web of Science:** 78
- **SBC:** 32
- **Scopus:** 193